

Oxidation of Acetyltetrahydroquinoline Sulphonic Acids.

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While studying the derivatives of cresol sulphonic acids and sulphohydroxybenzoic acids, attempts were previously made in this laboratory to synthesise 6-sulphosalicylic acid without success.

A new line of attack was suggested by the work of Zürcher (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 180) who recognised the formation of 2-amino-3-sulphobenzoic acid (very small yield). In the oxidation products of quinoline-8-sulphonic acid (Fischer and Renouf, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 755) Zürcher's acid was converted into the corresponding sulphosalicylic acid by Sucharda (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1927, 1, 3005). An attempt was, therefore, made to see whether the isomeric quinoline-5-sulphonic acid could be oxidised to yield the corresponding 2-amino-6-sulphobenzoic acid (or its derivative), which may ultimately be converted into the required sulphosalicylic acid. The attempt was, however, unsuccessful; only the formation of quinolinic acid, obtained by Fischer (*loc. cit.*), could be recognised.

It was, however, thought possible to get the derivatives of the amino-sulpho acids as main products of oxidation, if the quinoline sulphonic acids were first reduced, acetylated and then oxidised. The reduction was carried out with tin and hydrochloric acid, and the potassium salts of the tetrahydroquinoline sulphonic acids, thus obtained, could be easily acetylated by heating with acetic anhydride.

The oxidation of potassium acetyltetrahydroquinoline-8-sulphonate (I) with aqueous potassium permanganate at the ordinary temperature, gives a 60% yield of the acid dipotassium salt of 2-oxalyl-acetylamino-3-sulphobenzoic acid (II), and also a small quantity of the corresponding acid monopotassium salt (III). The compound (II) on heating for sometime with HCl solution (1:2), yields the acid monopotassium salt of 2-oxalylamino-3-sulphobenzoic acid (IV); but this, as well as the compound (II), gets decomposed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid. Potassium tetraoxalate was, however, recovered and identified and the dark bluish-red solution, on dilution with water, gives the characteristic blue fluorescence of the free amino-sulpho-acid which could not be recovered.

Oxidation of potassium acetyltetrahydroquinoline-5-sulphonate (V) under the same conditions (a very slow reaction) is found to proceed in two different directions. The major product is the dipotassium salt of 2-acetylamino-6-sulphobenzoylformic acid (VI), which when warmed with concentrated hydrochloric acid gives the potassium salt of the hitherto unknown isatin-4-sulphonic acid (VII). The preparation of free isatin sulphonic acid will be described in a separate communication.

The other substances obtained in small quantities are acid potassium salt of 2-acetylamino-6-sulphobenzoic acid (VIII) and probably the acid potassium salt of 2-amino-6-sulphobenzoic acid (IX) (*vide* experimental). The quantity of the last substance was very small and hence could not be thoroughly investigated. Potassium tetraoxalate was, however, recovered and identified showing that the oxidation in the direction of the intermediate formation of a compound (X) must have taken place, giving finally by further decomposition the products mentioned above. The total yield of the oxidation products in this case is small and an amount of dark red resinous material is obtained from which nothing could be isolated. This method, therefore, is not found to be a promising one for the synthesis of the required sulpho-salicylic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Quinoline-8-sulphonic acid and quinoline-5-sulphonic acid were prepared by the sulphonation of quinoline according to Riemer-Schmidt's method (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 721; *cf.* also Bedall and Fischer, *Ber.*, 1881, 14, 443; 1882, 15, 1979; Coste and Valeur, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 95). Since none of the authors give a precise quantitative data, the following details of the procedure will not only be found useful but more satisfactory for the isolation of the 5-acid.

Fuming H_2SO_4 (about 65% SO_3 , 300 g.) was added in portions to quinoline (100 g.), and the mixture heated at $130^\circ\text{--}140^\circ$ for 1 hour. The cooled mixture was poured into water (800 c.c.) and, after standing for 12 hours, the separated quinoline-8-sulphonic acid was filtered off, washed and recrystallised from water (95 g.). A saturated solution of 50 g. of HgCl_2 was then added to the acid filtrate; the separated thick flocculent precipitate was filtered off, washed, dissolved in hot water and decomposed by H_2S . The filtrate from HgS was concentrated, when the 5-acid crystallises on cooling in the form of needles, yield about 30 g. The HgCl_2 forms a double compound crystallising from water in clusters of small needles. (Found: Hg, 42.15. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{NS}$, HgCl_2 requires Hg, 41.66 per cent).

The above quinoline sulphonic acids (1 part) were reduced by pure tin (4 parts) and concentrated HCl (10 parts) (*cf.* Lellmann, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 3087; Claus, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1897, ii, 55, 94). The quinoline-5-sulphonic acid, as obtained above, always contains some impurity of the 8-isomeride, which ordinarily cannot be easily separated. The method of reduction, however, forms an excellent method for the complete separation of the two acids. Thus the tetrahydro-8-acid (very light leaflets, m.p. 245°) is more insoluble in hot water, particularly in HCl solution than the corresponding 5-acid (thick stout needles, m.p. $315^\circ\text{--}318^\circ$), and is thus easily removed.

Tetrahydroquinoline-8-sulphonic Acid.

Acetylation.—The finely powdered dry potassium salt was mixed with three times its weight of acetic anhydride and the mixture gradually heated in an oil-bath at $135^\circ\text{--}140^\circ$. The substance first dissolved (one hour) and was then immediately precipitated. The excess of anhydride was removed under reduced pressure (water-bath) and the solid washed with a mixture of absolute alcohol

and dry ether; almost pure product was obtained, yield theoretical. It is very soluble in water, difficultly soluble in alcohol. Potassium acetyltetrahydroquinoline-8-sulphonate crystallises from water by slow evaporation in the form of thick long needles. (Found: K, 13.22; H₂O, 8.1. C₁₁H₁₂O₄NSK, 1½H₂O requires K, 13.31; H₂O, 8.43 per cent. Found: S, 10.51. C₁₁H₁₂O₄NSK requires S, 10.92 per cent).

Oxidation of the Acetyl Compound.—10 G. of the above K-salt (I) were dissolved in 200 c. c. of water and KMnO₄ (26 g., 5% solution) was gradually added in portions; the liquid soon became warm, each portion was added after the first was decolourised. When the whole was added (8 hours) the mixture was heated on the water-bath for about 15 minutes (excess KMnO₄ removed by alcohol) and filtered hot; the filtrate after nearly neutralising with dilute H₂SO₄ was concentrated and the separated K₂SO₄ removed, until some organic substance began to separate along with it. The concentrated liquid was acidified with dilute HCl when short needles separated; a further quantity was obtained from the mother liquor on concentration, yield about 7.2 g. (II). The freshly crystallised substance partly effloresces in air. The air-dried substance was analysed. [Found: S, 8.07; H₂O (at 130°) 2.3. C₁₁H₇O₉NSK₂, ½H₂O requires S, 7.86; H₂O, 2.16 per cent. Found: K, 18.69; Equiv., 405.7. C₁₁H₇O₉NSK₂ requires K, 19.16 per cent. Equiv., 407.] From the final mother liquor on concentration a small quantity of a substance (III) crystallising in clusters of small needles was obtained. [Found: H₂O (at 130°), 6.7. C₁₁H₈O₉NSK, 1½H₂O requires H₂O, 6.81 per cent. Found: S, 8.99; Equiv., 185.1. C₁₁H₈O₉NSK requires S, 8.67 per cent. Equiv., 184.5.]

6 G. of the substance (II) were heated to boiling for half an hour with HCl solution (1:2), the solution turning pale brownish red. The products obtained are KCl, some undecomposed substance and a substance (IV, 1 g.), which crystallises from water in cauliflower-like crystals. (Found: H₂O, 7.59. C₉H₆O₈NSK, 1½H₂O requires H₂O, 7.62 per cent. Found: K, 12.02; Equiv., 163. C₉H₆O₈NSK requires K, 11.92 per cent. Equiv., 163.5).

When substance (II) or (IV) was heated with concentrated HCl instead of dilute solution, the substance decomposed completely giving a dark bluish solution; the separated KCl was removed and the acid liquid was allowed to evaporate spontaneously when thick plates were obtained.

This crystallises from water in thick stout long needles which burn away without charring, leaving a white residue. It also reduces acidified KMnO_4 solution. It is, therefore, potassium tetraoxalate. (Found : Equiv., 84.79. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}_8\text{K}$, 2 H_2O requires Equiv., 84.66).

The coloured liquid on dilution gives a blue fluorescence, but no substance could be recovered from it.

Tetrahydroquinoline-5-sulphonic Acid.

Acetylation.—The powdered K-salt was mixed with $1\frac{1}{2}$ times its wt. of acetic anhydride; good deal of heat was evolved in this case, the substance almost dissolved and then immediately separated out. The mixture was heated at 135° - 140° for 1 hour. It was worked up in the same way as the corresponding 8-derivative. Potassium acetyl-tetrahydroquinoline-5-sulphonate crystallises from water in thick plates, yield theoretical. (Found : S, 10.59; H_2O , 6.18. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{NSK}$, 1 H_2O requires S, 10.92; H_2O , 5.7 per cent. Found : K, 13.12. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ NSK requires K, 13.31 per cent).

Oxidation of the Acetyl Compound.—27 G. of the above K-salt (V) in 550 c. c. of water were gradually treated in the cold with a 5% solution of 70 g. of KMnO_4 over a period of 8 days. The solution was filtered without warming and the faintly yellowish filtrate was almost neutralised by dilute H_2SO_4 ; K_2SO_4 was removed by gradual concentration on a water-bath; finally the non-acidified concentrated liquid gave stout short white needles (7 g.) of a neutral substance containing potassium (VI). This was recrystallised three times from water and analysed. (Found : K, 21.62; H_2O , 6.65. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_7\text{NSK}_2$, $1\frac{1}{2}$ H_2O requires K, 21.48; H_2O , 6.92 per cent. Found : S, 9.13. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_7$ NSK₂ requires S, 8.81 per cent).

The mother liquor was concentrated over solid NaOH in a vacuum desiccator when, along with a further small quantity of the substance (VI), a greyish white powder was obtained (0.7 g.), which crystallises from water in microscopic silky needles (VIII); slightly soluble in cold, but easily in hot water. It is an acid potassium salt and does not give the isatin compound on treatment with concentrated HCl . It gives, however, an isocyanide reaction. It was twice recrystallised and analysed. (Found : S, 11.16; Equiv., 297.8. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_6\text{NSK}$ requires S, 10.77 per cent. Equiv., 297. Found : H_2O , 6.25. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$ NSK, 1 H_2O requires H_2O , 5.71 per cent.) The substance, therefore, is an acid potassium salt of 2-acetylamino-6-sulphobenzoic acid.

The final mother liquor, a reddish liquid, was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The reddish yellow sticky mass (about 20 g.) was treated in the cold with concentrated HCl when a pulpy mass separated; when recrystallised from water, short needles were obtained (about 0.2 g.) which do not give the isatin compound with HCl. It is also found to be an acid potassium salt and gives the isocyanide reaction. (Found: H_2O , 7.11. $C_7H_6O_5NSK$, H_2O requires H_2O , 6.60 per cent. Found: Equiv., 255.2. $C_7H_6O_5NSK$ requires Equiv., 255.) The substance, therefore, appears to be an acid potassium salt of 2-amino-6-sulphobenzoic acid.

The filtrate from the above was warmed when a small quantity of isatin sulphonic acid (K-salt) was obtained, some KCl and potassium tetraoxalate were also recovered. The rest was a brown resinous mass from which nothing could be isolated.

The substance (VI) is a dipotassium salt of 2-acetylamino-6-sulphobenzoylformic acid. When warmed with a strong solution of HCl, it was decomposed with the liberation of acetic acid yielding a granular yellowish substance on cooling. This was removed, washed and recrystallised twice from water as yellow short silky needles. It is a potassium salt of isatin-4-sulphonic acid (VII) since it gives indophenin reaction. It is moderately soluble in cold but easily in hot water, sparingly soluble in alcohol. The freshly recrystallised substance, if allowed to stand in contact with its mother liquor for a few days, changes into beautiful ruby-red prisms with no water of crystallisation. (Found: S, 12.38; K, 14.61. $C_9H_4O_5NSK$ requires S, 12.07; K, 14.71 per cent).

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